

IJAYUSH
International Journal of AYUSH
AYURVEDA, YOGA, UNANI, SIDDHA AND HOMEOPATHY
<http://internationaljournal.org.in/journal/index.php/ijayush/>

International Journal
Panacea
Research library
ISSN: 2349 7025

Original Research Article

Volume 11 Issue 3

May-June 2022

A PROSPECTIVE EXPERIMENTAL STUDY TO ASSESS THE THERAPEUTIC POTENTIAL OF MAGNESIUM GROUP VIS-À-VIS INDIVIDUALIZED HOMOEOPATHIC TREATMENT IN ORPHANAGE CHILDREN

Dr. Dariker Bateilin Kharmujai¹, Dr. Mukta Nivedita Bera²

¹PG Scholar, Department Of Materia Medica, A.M. Shaikh Homoeopathic Medical College, Hospital And P.G. Research Centre, Belgaum, Karnataka, India.

²PG Scholar, Department Of Materia Medica, A.M. Shaikh Homoeopathic Medical College, Hospital And P.G. Research Centre, Belgaum, Karnataka, India.

Email ID: muktanivedita07@gmail.com

Corresponding Author's Email ID: datheikhar@gmail.com

Abstract

Watching the troubles of children at orphanages has always been emotional disturbing event for us. These children are often neglected, the list of the basic amenities and individual need or deserves health care in these children has always been challenge to the state. The present work attempts to explore the service scope of homoeopathic medicines in these group of children. Over the last period of one and half years we have spoken to more than 5 care taker of different orphanages taken raw vital feedback from their experience of taking care of the orphans.

Dr Kent discovery of efficiency of magnesium carbonicum as a drug of choice in treatment of problems of orphans hinted towards increasing the scope of exploring how magnesium group drugs can be used in health problems seen in orphans (diarrhea, depression, anaemia, nutritional disorder).

Aim: To study the applicability of magnesium group drugs in the treatment of orphans children's and understanding the role of constitutional medicine in the orphans.

RESULTS: Subjects from both the group showed good results with the interventional treatment results were tabulated using chi-square test. Which had shown that From the magnesium group: subjects recovered: 6 (20%) Improved : 21 (70%) not improved : 03(16%). And From the constitutional group: Recovered: 6 (20%) Improved : 22(73%) Not improved: 02(6.66%)

CONCLUSION: Subjects under both groups have responded quite well to the interventional magnesium group of drugs helped the subjects with mood disturbances low immunity and recurrent infection, subjects under constitutional treatment also improved with similar problems.

Key words: magnesium group, orphans, comparative trial, individualized constitutional treatment.

INTRODUCTION:

Magnesium: It is a chemical element with symbol Mg and atomic number 12. It is a shiny gray solid which bears a close physical resemblance to the other five elements in the second column(group 2,or alkaline earth metals) of the periodic table: all group 2 elements have the same electron configuration in the outer electron shell and a similar crystal structure.

The magnesium group: 3rd row of periodic table **Identity and nourishment:** The issue of 3rd row follows separation and birth that is developing one's identity and expression of it like image, choice and ego. It is the stage where the child needs warmth, nourishment, care and emotional support. Also when children starts developing fears of natural, unknown and unfamiliar things and starts realizing the difference between the known and unknown. Wrong and right. There is also issue related to growth and development. Doing things for themselves At this stage children starts developing the ability to Take care of themselves and their basic needs and developing the ability to take decision for them, developing the ability to express. In the initial stages since they are not even sure of what they feel, what they want therefore they find it difficult to communicate.

DEFICIENCY : Due to excessive loss of Mg in urine, GI system disorders, that cause loss of Mg or and absorption or chronically low intake of Magnesium, Calcium depletion of calcium Heart spasm, nervousness and confusion, muscular excitability and kidney stones.

EXCESS: Mg toxicity associated with Kidney failure. A large dose of laxatives and antacid causes Mg excess.¹

Dr. Kent's experience in treating orphans and further the confirmatory use of this group of remedies by Dr Scholten to believe magnesium group is an invaluable asset in the management of problems of orphans. Dr. Kent came to magnesium group the classical way where after failing with number of children with diarrhea and killing a lot of children. He found an exact fitting picture in magnesium carbonicum and treated the children quite successfully. The phenomenon called "ORPHANS" is becoming increasingly complex and posing a threat to the existence of a civil society. In our country, there are countless children who still suffer from patronage without heart. Orphans are a hard fact and bitter truth of world. Treatment of orphans has always been a challenge and difficulty throughout history because of the inherent absence of caretaking parent and the family setting the child is often under a difficult and sometimes a harsh setting. In the absence of this, children suffer from emotional mental and bodily troubles and are less attended to by caretakers as hard as the government rules to be. There is no available instruction about a separate study carried out on Magnesium as a group in the treatment of diseases of orphans. This attempt to take this up and believe firmly that this work will explore the scope and add invaluable symptoms to the picture of magnesium as a drug of choice for people or children who live in the situation. Comparative study of magnesium group and individualized constitutional medicine in the management of diseases of orphans. Further working with the care taker and individually going through life history of every subject to understand both from individual as well as homoeopaths view was very heart touching and immensely rewarding were the experience to see the subject improve both with magnesium group remedies as well as constitutional remedies. Going back and forth into each history and exploring the scope of various remedies of magnesium group has certainly increased my understanding of the drugs. The magnesium group not jus helped the symptoms in prior literatures but also in conditions of bed wetting and chronic pharyngitis in children. Subjects in both the groups showed consistent improvement in approachability communication social confidence and in overall health. Since the entire study was carried out in 3 centers there were no cases lost follow up, though few children show little or no improvement.

The population of orphans has been increasing as a consequence of more families with children living in poverty. These children have an increased frequency of illness, including intestinal infections, anemia, neurologic disorders, seizures, behavioral disorders, mental illness, and dental problems, as increased frequency of trauma and substance abuse. These children are admitted to hospitals at a much higher rate than the national average have higher school failure rates, and the likelihood of their being victims of abuse and neglect is much higher. ²

Studies have shown that, 50% of such children were found suffering from illness, such as developmental delays, severe depression, or learning disorders. Rates of mental illness among these children are alarmingly high. In a study more than one quarter of these children found to have a major chronic mental illness, such as schizophrenia or substance abuse. ³

There are many diseases that take the lives of parents living in poverty around the world. This causes their children to become orphans, and then these same diseases also plague the children. The most common of these are HIV/AIDS, tuberculosis, malaria, and diarrhea-related illnesses.

Tuberculosis is another disease that affects orphaned children. It is the leading cause of death for people with AIDS, killing two million people each year. Tuberculosis is caused by a bacterium that is spread from person to person through droplets from a cough, sneeze, spit, laugh, or just someone speaking. Children often contract TB from adults, as most caretakers in orphanages have active TB and unknowingly spread it to the children. Malaria, another common disease with orphans, is contracted and spread by infected mosquitoes. If left untreated, this infection is often fatal, especially in children under five years of age. Diarrhea-related illnesses are another difficult issue millions of orphans must face. Contaminated food and drinking water is the main reason so many children end up with this. Every year 1.5 million people are killed by one of these illnesses. It is heart-breaking to think that millions of people are dying from diseases that could all be prevented or treated with the right medical care. The spread of HIV/AIDS could be stopped by getting children off the streets and into homes, tuberculosis can be treated with a drug that kills the bad bacteria in the body, malaria can be treated and prevented by medication, and diarrhea-related illnesses can all be prevented with clean food and drinking water. So what then is our part in all of this? We need to follow the Lord's commandments to care for the orphans. Taking care of their basic medical needs, I believe, is

the first step. Here in the United States we have all the necessary items to treat and prevent these diseases. We can make a huge difference in these kids' lives by supporting medical missions, going on missions ourselves, and by raising awareness of these diseases and how they are affecting orphans all over the world.⁴

It is heart-breaking to think that millions of people are dying from diseases that could all be prevented or treated with the right medical care. The spread of HIV/AIDS could be stopped by getting children off the streets and into homes, tuberculosis can be treated with a drug that kills the bad bacteria in the body, malaria can be treated and prevented by medication, and diarrhea-related illnesses can all be prevented with clean food and drinking water. So what then is our part in all of this? We need to follow the Lord's commandments to care for the orphans. Taking care of their basic medical needs, I believe, is the first step. Here in the United States we have all the necessary items to treat and prevent these diseases. We can make a huge difference in these kids' lives by supporting medical missions, going on missions ourselves, and by raising awareness of these diseases and how they are affecting orphans all over the world.⁵

EXPERIMENTAL

Martial and method -The comparative clinical trial was conducted in Belagavi on around 60 subjects, after an interview with the care taker of the orphanages informing the care taker and the subject about the interview process and details mentioned in the informed consent, subjects who met the criteria mentioned under inclusion and exclusion criteria were selected for the trial. The trial was carried out between May 1st 2020 to 30th November 2021. 60 subjects were divided into 2 groups irrespective of age , sex or problems they suffered. One group received magnesium group of remedies the other received indicated constitutional remedy.

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

TABLE NO.1:AGE INCIDENCE

This table shows the age incidence. The idea of such a statistical approach is to identify the age group with the highest incidence.

SL. NO	AGE GROUP	NO.OF CASES		PERCENTAGE	
		Mag - group	Constitutional group	Mag-group	Constitutional group
1.	05-10	16	18	47.05%	52.9%
2.	11-18	16	10	61.53	38.46%
TOTAL		60		100	

As shown in the above chart the maximum incidence was age group 5-10yrs that is 56.66% (34) cases, followed closely by the age group 11-18 yrs, that is 43.33%(26) cases.

TABLE NO.2: SEX INCIDENCE

From the above data we can infer that out of the 60 cases, 32 were male that is 53.33% of total no of cases & 28 were females that is 46.66% of the total no of cases.

SLNO	AGE GROUP	NO.OF CASES		PERCENTAGE	
		Mag-group	Constitutional group	Mag group	Constitutional group
1.	05-10	18	14	56.25%	43.75%
2.	11-18	12	16	42.85%	57.14%
TOTAL		60		100	

TABLE NO.3: MIASMATIC DIAGNOSIS:

SL NO	MIASM	NO.OF CASES		PERCENTAGE	
		Mag group	Constitutional group	Mag-group	Constitutional group
1.	Psora	14	19	42.4%	57.5%
2.	Psoro-sycosis	15	08	65.21%	34.78%
3.	Psoro-syphilis	01	03	25%	75%
TOTAL		60		100	

TABLE NO.4: MAGNESIUM GROUP REMEDIES

SL NO	REMEDIES	NO.OFCASES	PERCENTAGE
1	MAGNESIUM CARB	18	60%
2	MAGNESIUM MUR	05	16.66%
3	MAGNESIUM SULPH	04	13.33%
4	MAGNESIUM PHOS	03	10%
	TOTAL	30	100%

From the above tabulation, it is seen that in 60% (18) cases received magnesium carb.16.66% (05)cases received magnesium mur, 13.33%(04) cases received magnesium sulph,10%(03) received magnesium phos.

TABLE NO.5: CONSTITUTIONAL REMEDIES

This chart indicates the remedies indicated and the incidence of each in the 30 cases.

SL NO	REMEDIES	NO.OF CASES	PERCENTAGE
1	AGARICUS MUSCARIS	1	3.33%
2	INFLUENZINUM	5	16.66%
3	TUBERCULINUM	2	6.66%
4	PYROGENUM	1	3.33%
5	ARSENIC ALBUM	2	6.66%
6	CALCAREA CARB	3	10%
7	NATRUM MUR	3	10%
8	PULSATILLA	1	3.33%
9	PHOSPHORUS	2	6.66%
10	LACHESIS	1	3.33%
11	THUJA	1	3.33%
12	STRAMONIUM	2	6.66%
13	IGNATIA	1	3.33%
14	BELLADONNA	1	3.33%
15	NUX VOM	2	6.66%
16	BARYATA CARB	2	6.66%
	TOTAL	30	100%

This tabulation shows the indicated remedy for 30 cases, Influenzinum, calcarea carb, natrum mur, were the most frequently indicated remedies that is, 16.66%, 10%, respectively. 6.66% (2) cases closely followed by tube, ars alb, phos, stram, nux vom, baryta carb.3.33%(1)cases followed by bell, ignatia, thuja, laches is, puls, pyrogenum, agaricus.

TABLE NO.6: RESULTS OF TREATMENT OF MAGNESIUM GROUP

Sl. no	Remedies	Recovered	No. of cases improved	No. of cases not improved	Total no. of cases	Percentage (%)
1	MAG CARB	02	13	03	18	11%
2	MAG MUR	02	03	-	05	40%
3	MAG SULP	01	03	-	04	25%
4	MAG PHOS	01	02	-	03	33.33%
	TOTAL	06	21	03	30	20%
		30				

In this study, it was seen that 70% (21) cases showed improvement with magnesium group of remedies, 20% (06) cases showed complete recovery, and 10% (03) cases showed no improvement.

SL.NO	REMEDIES	NO.OFCASES	PERCENTAGE
1	RECOVERED	06	20%
2	IMPROVED	22	73%
3	NOT-IMPROVED	02	6.66%
	TOTAL	30	100%

TABLENO.7: RESULTS OF TREATMENT WITH CONSTITUTIONAL REMEDIES

In this study it was seen that 73% (22) cases showed complete improvement with constitutional remedies, 20% (06) cases showed complete recovery and 6.66% (02) cases showed no improvement.

RESULTS OF TREATMENT:

In magnesium group: out of 30 cases , maximum number of cases i.e, 21(70%) showed improvement , 06 (20%) cases showed complete recovery and 03(16%)cases were not improved. In constitutional approach out of 30 , maximum number of cases improved is22 (73%) with a feeling of mental and physical well-being,, 06 (20%) cases showed complete recovery, and 02 (6.66%) showed no improvement much as they improved initially for some time but later the condition came to a stand-still position, or the symptoms further relapsed.

This study clearly indicates the contribution of homoeopathic constitutional similimum as the main triggering force in the treatment of diseases suffered by orphans.

DISCUSSION

1. Age incidence: The highest incidence of diseases in orphans seen in the age group of 05-10 years that is 34 (56.66%) subjects. Around 11-18 yrs of age group number of cases is 26 (43.33%).

2. Sex incidence: In the study , male were found to be suffering more then females, as 53% (32) cases were male and 46.66% (38), cases were females. This also corroborates with the fact that males suffer more as compared to females.

3. Miasmatic background: An analysis of the group of symptoms indicates that they belong either to the psoric, psoro-sycotic or psoro-syphilitic, the initial symptomatology being essentially psoric. By administering the appropriate anti-psoric or anti-sycotic remedy, the group in question is cleared up and the original constitutional remedy reappears. A much better response follows the administration of that remedy now. The miasms are always mixed together in the individual, so that even when his attitude and appearance correspond more to one fundamental modulation, he will still inevitably contain traits and some or more manifestations of the other two, although at each age of his life one of the three miasms—psora, sycosis, syphilis—will dominate. In the present study 55% (33) cases had psora in background. 38% (23) cases had psoro-sycotic background. And only 6.66% (04) cases were psorosyphilitic background.

4. Magnesium group of remedies: As described by Dr Kent in the text book of lectures on material medica that magnesium carbonicum is the remedy of orphans as they have a tendency to sinking in the back of the head. The occiput bone will sink in, and the parietal terrible bones just come out over it and will be depression that not an uncommon thing in children that go into marasmus. They are very likely to have a potter's clay stools. Most of the rubrics related to constitutions is in the chapter sensations and complaints in general such as Constitution—carbonitrogenous, Constitution dyscratic, Constitution—hydrogenoid, Constitution—oxygenoid and so on.⁶ In clinical repertory by J.H. Clarke is divided into five chapters. One of them is repertory of the temperaments, dispositions, constitutions and states. In this chapter are given the remedies which have been found to act most beneficially in certain types of persons, temperaments, sex and age. There are also included complaints and conditions of particular type of persons and constitutions.⁷ Roberts bases his classification on the classical temperaments—nervous, bilious, sanguineous, phlegmatic—but cautions against typing by remedy: '...the remedy indicated by the conditions of disturbed balance is the one that will most quickly restore the equilibrium, regardless of the Temperament.'⁸ Ortega, however, takes a different slant on constitutional typing. 'The quest for the constitutional basis which modifies human suffering has been the task of all the great masters of medicine'⁹. Margery Blackie's statement, 'The constitutional remedy is a picture of the sum total of the strengths and weaknesses of the

person, mentally, emotionally and physically. It is in the early undiagnosable stages of illness that we must find the constitutional remedy.¹⁰ However, many people regard Vithoukka as one of the prime exponents of constitutional typing by remedy, resulting from his method of presenting remedies by their 'essences' and describing them in terms of patient personalities. Whether or not this was his original intention is not clear.¹¹ Whitmont himself offers the following definition — '... constitution is the inherent tendency to respond automatically along qualitatively predetermined individual, characteristic patterns. Constitutional differences are the differences of response patterns to identical situations.'¹² Sankaran devotes a chapter in *The Spirit of Homoeopathy* to the subject of 'Treating the Present State' in which he emphasises the need to treat the totality of the present. In this he distinguishes between previous states which have left their still visible imprint on the patient and presenting states in which what needs to be cured is the only reliable guide to the remedy.¹³

Constitutional remedy selected depending upon the following criteria which is to be perceived during case taking.

1. Predisposition factors.
2. Dispositional factors and their expression. Mental phase. Physical phase.
3. Diathesis.
4. Miasmatic background.
5. Totality of symptoms.
6. Individualisation.¹⁴

As we see in so many orphans the exact picture of the remedy Dr Kent described, so the whole magnesium group is taken under consideration depending upon the signs and symptoms we get. So here we have got the exact picture of 4 drugs i.e. Magnesium carb : 60% (18) cases. Magnesium muraticum: 16% (05) Magnesium sulph: 13.33% (4) Magnesium phos: 10% (3) cases. Constitutional remedies: Constitutional remedy is the remedy which belongs to the patient as a person and not only the disease. That's remedies are deep acting. These constitutional remedy varies from each patient to patient depending upon their individuality.

Constitutional remedy selected depending upon the following criteria which is to be perceived during case taking. As Hahnemann wrote, one must study the condition of the physical body and mental character as well as the occupational factors, lifestyles and habits, domestic and social relationships, age and sexuality and include this data in the case history. Boenninghausen made it clear in his case taking instructions that we must understand constitution and temperament and the other attendant circumstances so we know “who” we are treating. Hering reviewed the provings and clinical confirmations and included precise details on which remedies suited certain ages, sexes, diatheses, constitutions and temperaments in the chapter called Stages of Life and Constitutions found in his Guiding Symptoms. Jahr separated the symptoms common to the disease state from the constitutional concomitants of the patient and taught that these constitutional rubrics are often the most characteristic by nature. The constitutional medicines used for the treatment of the orphans were Agaricusmuscaris 3.33% (01), influenzinum 16.66% (05), tuberculinum 6.66% (2), pyrogenum 3.33% (1) , arsenic album 6.66% (2), calcarea carb 10% (3), natrum mur 10% (3), pulsatilla 3.33% (1), phosphorus 6.66% (2), lachesis 3.33% (1), thuja 3.33% (1) stramonium 6.66% (2) , ignatia 3.33% (1) , belladonna 3.33% (1) , nux vomica 6.66% (2) baryata carb 6.66% (2)

CONCLUSION This work considering conscientious and diligent observation made on 60 subjects and it's statistical outcome concludes that well selected homoeopathic remedy authentically choose on the basis of mental and physical generals and peculiar characteristic particulars can bring about the outstanding results. 60 subjects were divided into 2 groups, magnesium group and Constitutional remedies group which yielded positive outcome in 21 cases and 22 cases in magnesium and Constitution in both the group respectively. Secondly 6 cases individually got very good improvement of both the groups respectively where as 3 cases from magnesium group and 2 cases from the Constitutional group did not show any improvement. Constitutional treatment in orphan children has greatly helped in improving the quality of the life, taking care of mental as well as the physical plain. Whereas, magnesium group remedies has extensively helped in those children who were having great feeling of being forsaken and were depressed. The magnesium group has diminished those feelings and thus ensuring a better health. Though constitutional remedies displays a better results but

magnesium group of remedies also cannot be neglected specially in the diseases of orphans as it stands almost nearer to the Constitutional medicines. Though constitutional remedies and magnesium group remedies has outnumbered the other drugs in prescription, influenzzinum which was prescribed to the children having the history of sever viral infection, which helped in removing the blocks which was a hindrance on the way to complete cure.

Limitations of the study. Diseases of the orphans is not nearly a single disease but it ranges right from the mind till the discomfort of the body, it requires treatment which will heal the disease in all planes in orphans to restore a long affected morbid Constitution sufficient time is required.

Acknowledgements

We thank following orphanage homes ie, Swami Vivekanand Seva Pratishthan , Kiaan Children Home, Angel foundation, Belagavi, Karnataka for your hospitality. We are grateful to our institute A.M. Shaikh Homoeopathic Medical College, Hospital And P.G. Research Centre, Belgaum for encouraging us to take up this research. We express our gratitude to Dr. Afshan A Balekundri for her support and guidance who is our PG Guide and also HOD of Department Of Materia Medica. Last but not the least, our sincere thanks to all the subjects on whom the study was conducted.

REFERENCES

1. <http://wikipedia.com/magnesium> accessed on 12 /2/2022.
2. Behraman Richard E, Kliegmen Robert M, Arvin Ann.m: Nelson text book of pediatrics 15th edition book 1_1996: chapter 42. Page 137.
3. Wallace Robert B: public health and preventive medicine. 15th edition_ 2007: psychiatric disorder among homeless children page. 1166.
4. www.orphanhopeint.org/facts-statics.
5. [www//journey117.WordPress.com/2011/05/4/diseases-orphaned-children](http://www/journey117.WordPress.com/2011/05/4/diseases-orphaned-children).
6. Boger-Boenninhaisen's characterstic and repertory. Published by B Jain publishers page 62.
7. Henry John Clarke, clinical repertory to the dictionary of materia Medica, chapter temperament, disposition, constitution and state.
8. Robert. H. A The principles and art of cure by Homoeopathy published by B Jain publishers Pvt LTD. 1942. Page 170
9. Ortega, p.s, notes on miasm and Hahnemann's chronic diseases, new Delhi, 1980. Page 9-10
10. Blackie, classical Homoeopathy. Published by B Jain publishers Pvt LTD 1986 page 14
11. George Vithoukias. The science of Homoeopathy 1986 published by B Jain publishers Pvt LTD page 127.
12. Whitmont. Psyche and substance. Essay on Homoeopathy in the light of jungian psychology 1980 page 45.

13. Sankaran Rajan, the substance of Homoeopathy 1994. Published by Homoeopathic medical publishers page 27.
 14. Principles and practice of Homoeopathy, part-1, by Dr. M.L. Dhawale, MD. 3rd edition 2000, published by Institute of clinical research, mumbai, 284, 285, 307 page
-